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Paper Title	Understanding the Behavioural Factors Influencing Adoption of Sustainable Practices: Insights from Upland Beef and Sheep in Northern Ireland
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Abstract
<p>The aim of this study is to analyse the behavioural factors affecting the adoption of sustainable practices based on a survey of 357 beef and sheep farmers in Northern Ireland. The data are analysed using Partial Least Squares Structural Equation Modelling. Preliminary analyses show that 71 percent of the sampled farms have adopted sustainable farming practices, including replacing chemical fertilizers with manure/slurry, planting trees, hedgerows, and other nature-based solutions, implementing low-emission slurry spreading, reducing overall stocking density, introducing native/local breeds, and changing the mix of cattle and sheep. Preliminary results also identified the farmers' perceived attitude of farmers towards the environment, attitude towards risk, attitude towards profitability, and social influence as the main behavioural factors influencing adoption among beef and sheep farmers.</p>
Introduction
<p>Sustainable intensification poses one of the major challenges to agricultural production across the globe. The adoption of sustainable farming practices has been identified as a viable tool for farmers to increase their productivity while minimising environmental burdens. However, farmers tend to exhibit inertia towards adoption, resulting in low uptake rates across countries.</p> <p>At present, there is limited evidence regarding the factors that affect farmers' long-term commitment to the adoption of sustainable practices. This lack of understanding poses a challenge for achieving rapid and significant changes in the agri-food system. To this end, this paper seeks to fill this gap by identifying the behavioural factors that influence of adoption of sustainable practices.</p>
Methodology
<p>Relying on the theory of planned behaviour as the main framework, this paper analyses the behavioural factors underlying farmers' adoption of sustainable practices based on a survey of 357 beef and sheep farmers in Northern Ireland. The data are analysed using Partial Least Squares Path Modelling (PLS-PM), a widely used variance-based estimator for structural equation modelling (SEM) technique.</p>
(Preliminary) Results
<p>Preliminary analyses show that 71 per cent of the sampled farms have adopted sustainable farming practices, including replacing chemical fertilizers with manure/slurry, planting trees, hedgerows, and other nature-based solutions, implementing low-emission slurry spreading, reducing overall stocking density, introducing native/local breeds, and changing the mix of cattle and sheep. The results also show that insufficient subsidies/incentives, high costs of making changes, extremely strict regulations, uncertainty about environmental benefits, and</p>

lack of training are ranked as the most crucial barriers to the adoption of these practices. Finally, the preliminary results identified the farmers' perceived attitude of farmers towards the environment, attitude towards risk, attitude towards profitability, and social influence as the main behavioural factors influencing adoption of sustainable practices among beef and sheep farmers.

Discussion and Conclusion

In summary our preliminary analyses reveal that key influences on adoption include attitudes towards the environment, risk, and profitability, as well as farmers' social influences. However, barriers such as insufficient incentives, high costs, strict regulations, uncertainty about environmental benefits, and lack of training hinder broader adoption. Addressing these barriers and leveraging the identified behavioural factors can help design effective policies to promote long-term commitment to sustainable farming practices.